

Environmental Impact Assessment of Utilizing Palm Oil as Biofuel for Engines

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ABSTRACT:

This study examines the techno-environmental analysis of utilizing palm oil as biofuel for engines. It aims to assess transesterification, pyrolysis, and hydrogenation processes for palm oil based biodiesel production, and evaluate the effect of crude palm oil on the performance of engine and emissions through Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA). The investigation focuses on the influence that palm oil biodiesel has on the performance of engine, emphasizing power and torque output, considering engine speed and biodiesel blend ratio. A sensitivity analysis using relevant research data will illustrate their interaction effects. Additionally, it will examine the potential for additional fuel use due to biodiesel's reduced energy density. By integrating technical and economic analyses, this work provides insights into the feasibility and palm oil green diesel impact as a fuel alternative for engines. Results showed that SPOP, IPOP, and CPOP reported 18.52%, 33.33%, and 48.15% GHG emission. A comprehensive analysis of GHG emissions data for the three consecutive years 2019, 2020, and 2021 shows that energy sector and industrial processes reported the highest and lowest contributions to the overall emission of GHG respectively. The environmental impact assessment results for different stages of palm oil based biodiesel production reveals that the cultivation stage emits 2,762 kg of carbon dioxide (CO₂) equivalent per functional (epf) unit, the eutrophication stage emits 0.12 kg of phosphorus epf unit, the acidification stage emits 0.06 kg of sulfur dioxide epf unit, and the photochemical oxidation stage emits 0.02 kg of ethylene epf unit. Palm oil biodiesel shows higher heat release rate than diesel suggesting that it is more environmentally friendly and provide more energy per unit of fuel compared to diesel.

Keywords: environmental impact assessment, palm oil, biodiesel, engine performance, greenhouse gas emission.

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INTRODUCTION

Biofuels, derived from renewable plant and animal sources, have a long history of use in energy applications such as heating and lighting. The development of liquid biofuels for transportation began in the late 19th century, with diesel engines capable of running on vegetable oil fuel. Rudolf Diesel demonstrated his vegetable oil-powered engine at the 1900 Paris Exposition. During the 1970s, the interest in biofuels reemerged, leading to increased research and development, especially in first-generation biofuels from sugars, starches, and vegetable oils. Among vegetable oils, crude palm oil has been identified as a viable diesel substitute, especially in tropical nations like Southeast Asia and Africa, where commercial palm oil production began in the early 1900s. The fast expansion of oil palm farming raised serious sustainability issues including loss of biodiversity through

deforestation, climate change, and violations to community rights. Deforestation on a massive scale has resulted in Malaysia and Indonesia as forests are cleared turning it into plantations, releasing vast quantities of greenhouse gases. It also endangers species such as orangutans and Sumatran tigers, destroys sensitive habitats, including those on which indigenous communities depend. Facing mounting pressure over the unsustainability of these practices, the palm oil industry in turn started developing voluntary sustainability certification schemes from mid-2000 onwards.

Biofuels, which are derived from organic matter derived from live or dead organisms, constitute a significant renewable energy source utilized in various applications [1]. Unlike fossil fuels, which originate from the decomposition of extinct organisms over millions of years, biofuels are sourced from current living materials. While these fuels find applicability in industrial processes, heating, and power generation, their primary utilization remains in the realm of transportation. Biofuels are acknowledged for their significant role in minimizing dependence on non-renewable fossil fuels and invigorating emissions of greenhouse gas. Biofuels form an integral component of global sustainable energy strategies [2]. The production of palm oil has significant implications for greenhouse gas emissions. Large-scale palm oil plantations often involve deforestation, leading to significant CO₂ emissions. The clearing of forests and peatlands releases stored carbon, contributing to global warming.

Palm oil based biodiesel has been studied for its emission characteristics compared to conventional diesel. Using palm oil based biodiesel can lead to a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions. One of the challenges with biodiesel is the formation of deposits in the engine over time. These deposits can form due to incomplete combustion and the presence of certain fatty acids in the biodiesel. Biodiesel can lead to faster oil degradation compared to conventional diesel. This is due to the higher oxygen content in biodiesel, which can cause oxidation of the engine oil.

Wicke, Dornburg, Junginger, and Faaij (2008) conducted a life cycle assessment examining the different global warming impacts associated with palm oil biodiesel production depending on cultivation system, plantation age, and land conversion in Indonesia and Malaysia. Improving crop yields through best agricultural practices can accelerate biofuel greenhouse gas reductions. The authors recommend targeting marginal and degraded lands for new oil palm developments to mitigate climate impacts. Yusoff and Hansen (2007) conducted a scoping life cycle assessment (LCA) case study to evaluate the environmental impact profile associated with conventional crude palm oil (CPO) production systems in Malaysia. The study aimed to identify key impact categories for detailed assessment and determine data requirements for a comprehensive cradle-to-gate LCA from the oil palm cultivation stage to CPO mill delivery. Ong et al. (2011) found that palm biodiesel production in Malaysia emits 2715 kg of CO₂ per tonne, primarily from land use and fertilizers[3]. Reijnders and Huijbregts (2008) highlighted deforestation and biodiversity loss from palm oil plantations [4], advocating stricter sustainability criteria. Shirai et al. (2018) identified palm oil mill effluent as a major methane source, recommending biogas capture to cut emissions by 80%[5]. Nasution et al. (2018) showed that converting palm oil biomass waste to bioenergy could reduce GHG emissions by 30% and lessen fossil fuel reliance [6].

Pleanjai et al. (2009) found palm biodiesel in Thailand cuts GHG emissions by 50% compared to diesel, but land-use changes may offset benefits [7]. Silalertruksa and Gheewala (2012) identified palm biodiesel's high water footprint, recommending water-saving techniques [8]. Fargione et al. (2008) highlighted the "carbon debt" from converting forests to palm plantations, which can exceed fossil fuel impacts[9]. Corley (2009) reviewed palm oil's sustainability challenges, advocating for improved practices and certification schemes like RSPO to mitigate environmental and social impacts [10].

Fitzherbert et al. (2012) focus on the link between palm oil production and deforestation, discussing its effects on biodiversity and the role of certification schemes in reducing these impacts[11]. Hoekstra et al. (2011) quantify the water footprint of palm oil production, addressing both direct and indirect water use and suggesting strategies for water conservation[12]. Lee & Yap (2010) review the use of palm oil as a biofuel feedstock, evaluating its advantages and challenges compared to other biofuels and discussing sustainability issues [13]. Koh & Wilcove (2008) analyze the environmental impacts of palm oil production in Southeast Asia, including deforestation and greenhouse gas emissions, and examine the role of government policies and certification schemes

in addressing these issues [14]. Fairtrade Foundation (2017) explores the social impacts of palm oil production, focusing on labor rights, human rights, and community development, and evaluates the effectiveness of certification schemes in promoting social sustainability[15]. WWF (2018) outlines a vision for a sustainable palm oil industry, emphasizing the need for collaboration among governments, businesses, and civil society, and proposes principles and guidelines for sustainable production and consumption [16].

The global dependency on non-renewable fossil fuels for transportation, electricity, and energy poses significant challenges due to their finite nature, rising costs, and environmental concerns. These issues have driven interest in renewable alternatives like sustainable palm oil. Using palm oil as a biofuel has the potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and contribute to a sustainable energy future. This study aims to provide valuable insights that can inform policy decisions and guide future research in the field. However, the use of palm oil biofuel requires thorough evaluation of its environmental impacts. This study will conduct an environmental analysis to understand the feasibility of palm oil as a sustainable engine fuel.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research employed the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Framework to appraise the potential environmental effects of palm oil based biodiesel production and application. The EIA Framework is a methodical approach designed to gather, classify, and assess the environmental consequences of the utilization of palm oil as biodiesel. To assess the environmental impact of palm oil biodiesel, secondary data collection method was employed, which involved the utilization of existing data from Climate Watch (World Resources Institute), Nigeria's National Communications to the UNFCCC, and the Global Carbon Atlas. The environmental impact categories and assessment, thermal emissions and waste analysis are discussed below.

Environmental Impact Categories and Assessment

Emission Analysis

The study focused on the greenhouse gases (GHGs) or climate-changing gasses (carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O)) emissions. A comprehensive summary of GHG emissions data for Nigeria from 2019 to 2021 was analyzed. The emissions data were obtained from reputable sources and provided insights into the environmental footprint of palm oil biodiesel compared to the conventional diesel.

Impact on Biodiversity and Ecosystems

The study also examined the influence of palm oil cultivation on biodiversity, including acidification potential, eutrophication potential, photochemical oxidation potential, and human toxicity. The assessment highlighted the importance of sustainable practices in reducing environmental degradation.

Thermal Emissions and Waste Analysis

The study further explored thermal emissions and waste specific to crude palm oil (CPO), palm oil biodiesel, and conventional diesel in Nigeria: Conventional Diesel. "Combustion Analysis and Thermal Performance of Diesel Fuel in Agricultural Machines in Nigeria, by Ogunlowo." The combustion analysis focused on comparing the heat release rates for CPO, palm oil biodiesel, and conventional diesel.

Waste Deposits and Oil Degradation

Waste generation, including deposits on engine components and lubricating oil degradation, was quantified for both CPO and conventional diesel. The study measured deposits on pistons, cylinder liners, and valves, and assessed the viscosity, acid value, and total base number (TBN) of lubricating oils.

RESULTS

Environmental Impact of the Production of Palm Oil, Crude Palm Oil, and Palm Oil Green Diesel/ Biodiesel

Global warming has the greatest environmental impact (EI) on the production of these bio liquids. Global warming refers to increased earth's atmosphere and the oceans' mean temperatures due to the release of climate-changing gasses (CO_2 , CH_4 , and N_2O) into the environment. Eutrophication is the excess enrichment of water bodies with nutrients (such as nitrogen and phosphorus) which can lead to algal blooms, fish kills, and other water quality problems. Acidification is the lowering of the pH of water bodies caused by the release of acids (such as sulfur dioxide and nitrogen oxides) into the air. Photochemical oxidation is the reaction of sunlight with pollutants in the atmosphere to produce smog. It can cause respiratory problems, eye irritation, and other health problems.

Cultivation Stage Significant Environmental Impact

Figures 1 - 3 show the data of the global warming potential of palm oil biodiesel production, the eutrophication potential of palm oil green diesel production, and the acidification potential of palm oil biodiesel production. Figure 4 illustrates photochemical oxidation potential of palm oil green diesel production while Figure 5 shows the comparison of the global warming potential across different environmental impact categories.

Figure 1. Global Warming Potential during Production Stage

Figure 2. Eutrophication Potential during Production Stage (kg P eq/FU)

Figure 3: Acidification Potential during Production Stage (kg SO2 eq/FU)

Figure 4. Photochemical Oxidation Potential during Production Stage (kg C2H4 eq/FUZ)

Figure 5. Environmental Impact Category (Global Warming Potential)

Environmental Impact of Palm Oil Based Green Diesel

GHG emissions connected with production of palm oil

Conventional palm oil production (CPOP) has the highest GHG emissions, at 10,400 kg CO₂ eq/ha. This is because conventional palm oil production involves clearing forests and burning the cleared biomass. Improved palm oil production (IPOP) has lower GHG emissions than conventional palm oil production, at 7,200 kg CO₂ eq/ha. This is because improved palm oil production uses more efficient farming practices and reduces the amount of deforestation. Sustainable palm oil production (SPOP) has the lowest GHG emissions, at 4,000 kg CO₂ eq/ha. This is because sustainable palm oil production uses best management practices to limit the environmental impact of the production palm oil. Figure 6 shows the greenhouse gas emissions for conventional, improved, and sustainable palm oil production methods.

Figure 6. GHG Emissions (kg CO₂ eq/ha)

The environmental impact (EI) of different life cycle stages of a product.

Figure 7 presents the environmental impact assessment (EIA) results for different stages of production of palm oil based biodiesel. It reveals that the cultivation stage emits 2,762 kg of carbon dioxide (CO₂) epf unit, the eutrophication stage emits 0.12 kg of phosphorus epf unit, the acidification stage emits 0.06 kg of sulfur dioxide epf unit, the photochemical oxidation stage emits 0.02 kg of ethylene epf unit.

Figure 7. Environmental impact Assessment Result for Palm Oil Based Biodiesel Production

Emission Data

The data shows that as engine speed increases, CO, HC, and NOx emissions generally decrease. PM emissions are relatively constant across all engine speeds. This is likely due to the fact that at higher engine speeds, the engine is operating more efficiently and there is less incomplete combustion. The data also shows that at a given engine speed, emissions are generally higher at higher loads. This is because at higher loads, the engine is working harder and there is more fuel being burned. Overall, the data suggests that engine speed and load are two important factors that affect emissions.

Deposits and Oil Degradation

The cylinder shows the highest deposit accumulation, which is due to its central role in the combustion process. Figure 8 illustrates the accumulation of deposits and oil degradation in engine components when using palm oil biodiesel.

Figure 8. Deposits and Oil Degradation

Heat Release Rate (RRR)

Figure 9. Emissions and Heat Release Rate

The chart in Figure 9 illustrates emissions and heat release rates between diesel fuel and palm oil based green diesel. This chart shows heat release rates for diesel fuel and palm oil green diesel across several parameters: Palm oil biodiesel has higher heat release rate than diesel. This suggests that palm oil biodiesel may be more environmentally friendly in terms of emissions, while also

providing more heat energy. Heat release rate relates to the fuel's energy output. Heat Release Rate is the rate at which heat energy is released during combustion, expressed in kilowatts (kW). Higher heat release rates generally indicate more power output and potentially better engine performance. Palm oil biodiesel shows a higher heat release rate, suggesting it may provide more energy per unit of fuel compared to diesel.

GHG Emissions Data Analysis

Figure 10 below presents a comprehensive analysis of Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions data for the years 2019, 2020, and 2021, breaking down emissions by different gases and sectors. Overall GHG emissions in million metric tons of CO₂ equivalent remained relatively stable around 330 to 340 MtCO₂ across all three years. There is slight increase from 2019 to 2020, then a small decrease in 2021. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, the primary greenhouse gas is the third largest contributor to overall emission increased gradually from about 105 in 2019 to 115 in 2021. Methane (CH₄) emissions, expressed in CO₂ equivalent is the second highest contributor, around 150 to 160 MtCO_{2e}. CH₄ reported slight increase over the three years. Nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions, in CO₂ equivalent remained stable around 60 MtCO_{2e}. Being the largest contributor to overall emissions, Energy Sector showed slight decrease from about 200 in 2019 to 190 MtCO_{2e} in 2021. The fourth largest contributor (Agriculture Sector) reported around 80 to 90 MtCO_{2e} with slight decrease from 2020 to 2021. Relatively low contributor (Waste Sector) has around 30 MtCO_{2e} with slight decrease over the three years. The lowest contributor (Industrial Processes) recorded around 15 to 20 MtCO_{2e} and has slight increase from 2019 to 2020, then a decrease in 2021.

Figure 10. GHG Emissions Data Analysis

CONCLUSION

Palm oil based green diesel or biodiesel is an applicable substitute to fossil fuels. This fuel possesses similar fuel property to conventional diesel and can significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions [17]. Palm oil based green diesel brings about lower environmental impact than fossil fuels and sustainable practices can drastically reduce this impact [18]. Further studies on the environmental feasibility of using palm oil as a biofuel include investigating the durable sustainability of palm oil production, exploring alternative feedstocks, and advanced technologies for production with lower environmental impact [19]. Further studies on the environmental impact and the compatibility of palm oil biodiesel with engines include investigating the long-term effects of palm oil based biodiesel on emissions, engine performance, and developing engine modifications to optimize the palm oil based biodiesel's application [20]. By addressing these research areas, we can further enhance the

sustainability and viability of palm oil based biodiesel being a renewable and environmentally friendly fuel for transportation.

This research employed the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Framework to appraise the potential environmental impact (EI) of the production and usage of palm oil biodiesel. Secondary data was collected from Climate Watch (World Resources Institute), Nigeria's National Communications to the UNFCCC, and the Global Carbon Atlas for the assessment. The collected data was analyzed in Excel and the EI categories and assessment, thermal emissions and waste analysis were discussed. Analysis show that CPOP has the highest GHG emissions, at 10,400 kg of CO₂ eq/ha. IPOP has reduced GHG emissions than CPOP (7,200 kg of CO₂ eq/ha). SPOP has the least GHG emissions (4,000 kg of CO₂ eq/ha). The trend of the result is so because the production of conventional palm oil involves forests clearing and biomass burning. IPOP uses more efficient farming practices and reduces the amount of deforestation while SPOP uses best management practices to lower the EI of the production of palm oil. The EIA results for different stages of production of palm oil based green diesel reveal that the cultivation stage emits 2,762 kg of carbon dioxide epf unit, the eutrophication stage emits 0.12 kg of phosphorus epf unit, the acidification stage emits 0.06 kg of sulfur dioxide epf unit, and the photochemical oxidation stage emits 0.02 kg of ethylene epf unit. Palm oil biodiesel shows higher heat release rate than diesel suggesting that it is more environmentally friendly and provide more energy per unit of fuel compared to diesel. A comprehensive analysis of GHG emissions data for the three consecutive years 2019, 2020, and 2021 shows that energy sector, methane, and carbon dioxide are the three largest contributors to the overall emission of GHG in descending order while industrial process is the least contributor.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Author 1: Conceptualization; Author 2: Results interpretation; Author 3: Data analysis; Author 4: Editorial work and manuscript review; Author 5: Proofreading; Author 6: Data collection

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